

CPP-ACP And Its Effectiveness on White Spot Lesions in Pediatric Patients: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: White spot lesions (WSLs), the earliest sign of enamel demineralization, affect up to 50% of children and can progress to caries if untreated. CPP-ACP is a non-invasive remineralizing agent that delivers bioavailable calcium and phosphate to the enamel surface. While its potential is to reverse the course of caries, evidence specific to pediatric populations remains limited. This systematic review evaluates the effectiveness of CPP-ACP in treating WSLs in pediatric patients. **Aim:** To evaluate the effectiveness of CPP-ACP in the treatment of white spot lesions in pediatric patients. **Materials and Methods:** A comprehensive electronic search was performed across PubMed, PubMed Central, Google Scholar, EBSCO Host, Scopus, and grey literature from database inception to 17 August 2024. A PubMed search strategy was adapted for all databases using MeSH terms and Boolean operators. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) evaluating CPP-ACP for treatment of WSLs in children aged 1–15 years were included. In vitro studies, reviews, studies not involving CPP-ACP, and preventive-only orthodontic protocols were excluded. Two reviewers independently screened studies, assessed eligibility, extracted data, and evaluated risk of bias using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 (RoB 2) tool. The study selection process followed PRISMA guidelines (PROSPERO: CRD42024580513). **Results:** A total of 2,807 records were identified; 6 RCTs (n = 377 children) met inclusion criteria. Follow-up ranged from 12 weeks to 12 months. All included studies demonstrated improvement in WSL regression or appearance following CPP-ACP use. Combined CPP-ACP and fluoride formulations generally showed superior outcomes compared with fluoride alone. Varnish-based CPP-ACP achieved faster responses, while daily home-use CPP-ACP produced gradual but sustained improvements. Evidence was strongest for smooth-surface lesions. **Conclusion:** CPP-ACP is an effective non-invasive therapy for remineralizing white spot lesions in pediatric patients, with enhanced benefit when combined with fluoride. However, heterogeneity in outcome measures, small sample sizes, and variable follow-up durations limit the strength of conclusions. Larger, standardized RCTs with uniform diagnostic criteria are needed..

Keywords: White spot lesions, Casein phosphopeptide-amorphous calcium phosphate, Resin infiltration, Fluoride varnish, Pediatric dentistry

INTRODUCTION

White spot lesions (WSLs) are the earliest clinical indicators of dental caries. They appear as chalky, opaque enamel areas that become more visible when teeth are dried (1,2). Fejerskov et al defined the words "initial" or "incipient" lesions are used in conjunction with the term "white spot lesion" (WSL), as "the first sign of caries lesion on enamel that can be detected with the naked eye." (3) These lesions result from subsurface demineralization, while the outer enamel

layer may remain intact (1, 4). The underlying cause is predominantly the activity of acid-producing bacteria in dental plaque, which metabolize fermentable carbohydrates and causes mineral loss (5, 6). Epidemiological studies show that the prevalence of WSLs in the general population ranges from approximately 10% to 49% (1, 7). In orthodontic patients prevalence of WSL is highly variable, ranging from 2% to 96% as the plaque accumulation is higher due to fixed appliances (8, 9). Recent study observed a significant increase in visible WSLs

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

during the COVID-19 pandemic, rising from 29.5% to 52.8%, likely due to disruptions in routine dental care and altered oral hygiene and dietary habits (10). It is most frequently observed in adolescents and it shows slight male predominance in some studies. It develops rapidly, sometimes within just four weeks after the placement of fixed orthodontic appliances (8, 11).

Dental caries is most common oral disease globally and represents a major public health issue, with millions affected by untreated lesion in both primary and permanent teeth (12). Caries is a multifactorial condition influenced by microbial biofilms, frequent sugar intake, host susceptibility, and time. It initiates with demineralization beneath an intact enamel surface, leading to increased porosity and the appearance of chalky white areas. If left unmanaged, WSLs can progress to cavitation with irreversible enamel loss (5, 12). Typically, WSLs develop in two stages: initial surface softening and mineral loss, followed by subsurface lesion progression as demineralization penetrates deeper into the enamel (4, 13, 14). The principle of WSL management is to arrest or reverse early demineralization through remineralization strategies. Optimal oral hygiene, including twice-daily brushing, flossing, and dietary modifications, is essential.(15,16) Fluoride continues to be a main preventive agent in pediatric dentistry, promoting the formation of fluorapatite, a mineral more resistant to acid dissolution. Adjunctive therapies such as antimicrobial mouth rinses help reduce cariogenic bacterial load, while xylitol-containing gums and lozenges stimulate salivary flow and neutralize acids.(17) Central to enamel remineralization is the availability of bioactive calcium and phosphate ions. For fluoride to exert its full remineralizing potential, particularly in subsurface lesions, an appropriate calcium-to-phosphate molar ratio (ideally between 1:1 and 1.66:1) is required. (21,22) Casein phosphopeptide–amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP), a milk-derived compound, has emerged as a promising non-invasive remineralization agent. The CPP component stabilizes amorphous calcium phosphate nanocomplexes and localizes them at the enamel surface and within the salivary pellicle, creating a reservoir of bioavailable minerals in close proximity to the demineralized enamel. (23-25) This sustained

supersaturation facilitates diffusion of calcium and phosphate into the lesion body, enhancing remineralization. Moreover, CPP-ACP has demonstrated antimicrobial properties by inhibiting *Streptococcus mutans*, thereby contributing to further caries prevention.(25-27)

Clinically, CPP-ACP has been shown to be effective in managing early WSLs, enamel hypomineralization, mild fluorosis, dentinal hypersensitivity, and initial stages of erosion. Its anti-cariogenic and anti-plaque properties make it particularly beneficial in managing young patients. (28) Commercially available products such as MI Paste and MI Paste Plus (containing CPP-ACP and CPP-ACPF respectively) deliver these bioactive minerals in a user-friendly topical format. The combination of CPP-ACP with fluoride (CPP-ACPF) exerts a synergistic effect, enhancing remineralization by simultaneously supplying calcium, phosphate, and fluoride ions, making it a valuable adjunct in modern preventive pediatric dentistry. (29,30) Although numerous studies have investigated the effectiveness of remineralizing agents and CPP-ACP in general populations, there is a lack of focused evidence specifically evaluating its use in pediatric patients. Therefore, this systematic review was conducted to assess the effectiveness of CPP-ACP in the treatment and prevention of white spot lesions in pediatric patients.

Reporting Guidelines:

This systematic review was carried out using the Preferred Reported Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) guidelines and was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42024580513).

Review Question:

The research question, based on the Participants Intervention Comparison Outcome format was “What is the effectiveness of CPP-ACP in treatment of white spot lesions in pediatric patients?”

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Protocol Registration

This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-

Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines and was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42024580513). No amendments were made after registration.

2.2 PICO and eligibility criteria

Population:

Children aged **1–15 years** with clinically diagnosed white spot lesions (ICDAS 1–2).

Intervention:

Topical casein phosphopeptide–amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP) in any delivery form.

Comparison:

Fluoride varnish, CPP-ACPF, resin infiltration, placebo, or standard oral hygiene.

Outcomes:

Primary—reduction in WSL severity (lesion size, ICDAS score, or validated clinical index). Secondary—esthetic improvement, lesion activity changes, dmft/dmfs changes.

Inclusion criteria-

- Randomized controlled trials (RCTs).
- In vivo studies.
- Pediatric populations (1–15 years).
- Articles in English (2010–2024).

- CPP-ACP used for **treatment** of WSLs.

Exclusion criteria-

- In vitro / in situ / animal studies.
- Studies limited to orthodontic prevention protocols.
- Studies not evaluating CPP-ACP.
- Review articles, editorials, book chapters.
- Studies with adult participants.

2.3 Information sources and search strategy

A systematic electronic search was done on various electronic search engines- PubMed, Google Scholar, Grey literature, EBSCOHost database with the relevant key words and MeSH terms related to “Incipient caries lesion OR early enamel caries OR white spot lesions AND CPP-ACP OR Tooth mousse OR remineralization and Pediatric patient OR children”, “was applied along with AND/OR boolean operators. An additional manual search was performed by examining the reference lists of relevant studies and review articles. The search approach utilized both controlled vocabulary and free-text terms, initially designed for MEDLINE and subsequently adjusted for use with other databases

Table 1: Search List of Articles

PUBMED Central	"((Incipient caries lesion OR early enamel caries OR white spot lesions) AND (CPP ACP OR Tooth mousse OR remineralization) AND (Pediatric patient OR children) NOT (adult))"	1601
GOOGLE SCHOLAR	"((Incipient caries lesion OR early enamel caries OR white spot lesions) AND (CPP ACP OR Tooth mousse OR remineralization) and (Pediatric patient OR children))"	646
SCOPUS	"((Incipient caries lesion OR early enamel caries OR white spot lesions) AND (CPP ACP OR Tooth mousse OR remineralization) and (Pediatric patient OR children))"	428
PUBMED	"((Incipient caries lesion OR early enamel caries OR white spot lesions) AND (CPP ACP OR Tooth mousse OR remineralization) AND (Pediatric patient OR children) NOT (adult))"	99
EBSCOHost	"((Incipient caries lesion OR early enamel caries OR white spot lesions) AND (CPP ACP OR Tooth mousse OR remineralization) AND (Pediatric patient OR children) NOT (adult))"	30

Study Selection

A total of 2807 articles were initially identified through various sources, including Google Scholar (n = 646), PubMed (n = 99), PubMed Central (n = 1601), EBSCOHost (n=30), Scopus(n=428) and grey literature (n = 3). After removing 314 duplicate records, 2,493 articles were screened for relevance by reading titles and abstracts. Of these, 645 records were excluded at the title/abstract screening stage. Subsequently, 1,845 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. During this process, 1,839 articles were excluded for the following reasons: studies including patients above 15 years (n = 234), in vitro studies, narrative reviews, review articles, and systematic reviews (n = 1,217), studies not available in English (n = 19), and studies not comparing CPP-ACP (n = 369). Ultimately, 6 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final systematic review.

Data Extraction:

Data extraction was done by one reviewer through a pre-formed data extraction form in Excel and rechecked by a blinded reviewer. The study characteristics collected were authors, country, year, study design, population, intervention, comparison and outcomes. The characteristics of these six studies are summarized in Table 1.

Quality Assessment and Data Synthesis

The Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews for Interventions 5.1.0 was used to assess the risk of bias of every retrieved study included. The assessment tool included blinding of assessment, random sequence generation, selective reporting, incomplete outcome data, allocation concealment, and other plausible origins of bias to estimate the methodological constitution of studies included. Within every study, bias was sub-divided as “low risk of bias,” “high risk of bias” as well as “unclear risk of bias.” Cochrane Review Manager Version 5.4 (Cochrane library) was used to generate risks of bias Figures. The study characteristics were extracted according to the data extraction form prepared on Excel. The following data were recorded for each study: author, year, number of participants, age and follow up protocol, intervention, comparison and finally the outcome of study.

RESULTS

Study Characteristics

Six randomized controlled trials (Table 1) were included in this review, assessing a total of 377 children aged between 1 year and 15 years. The duration of follow-up ranged from 12 weeks to 12 months. All participants were systemically healthy and presented with white spot lesions (WSLs) due to various etiologies, including early childhood caries and post-orthodontic demineralization. The interventions studied across the trials included casein phosphopeptide-amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP), and comparison include CPP-ACP combined with fluoride (CPP-ACFP), fluoride varnish, and other fluoride-containing agents.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flowchart for screening and selecting articles

Risk of Bias and Quality Assessment

Studies 2 and 5 showed an unclear risk of bias, while the remaining studies (1, 3, 4, and 6) demonstrated a low risk of bias (Fig 2). The randomization process was the most consistently low-risk domain, observed in 75% of the studies. In contrast, incomplete outcome data contributed the most to the risk of bias, with a high-risk proportion of 37.5% (Fig 3). The overall study quality varied notably. Using the QATSD tool (maximum score: 42), individual study scores ranged from 23 to 36, with an average score of 27.3 (Fig 4). Some quality indicators were well addressed, such as the alignment between research questions and the methods of data collection and analysis. However, no studies reported user or patient involvement in their design, and most lacked a clearly defined theoretical framework. Other less robust areas included sample size justification and assessment of the reliability and validity of measurement tools. Agreement between independent reviewers was 85.7% (72/84), with a weighted kappa of 0.83 (95% CI: 0.68–0.94), indicating good inter-rater concordance.

Figure 2: Risk of Bias

Figure 3: Quality Assessment

Outcome of the Studies

CPP-ACP has been shown to significantly enhance remineralization and improve the appearance of white spot lesions in pediatric patients. It is more effective than fluoride alone, especially when combined with fluoride varnish or gel.

Table 2: Result Table

Author and year	Country	Study Design & Follow-up	Population and follow up	Intervention	Comparision	Outcomes Measured	Key Findings
Memarpour et al., 2015	Iran	Double-blind RCT, 12 months	140 children (12–36 mo) with primary tooth WSLs	CPP-ACP applied daily	Placebo; oral hygiene only; 5% NaF varnish	WSL area, dmft, lesion activity	CPP-ACP showed greatest reduction in WSL area and dmft index.
Llena et al., 2015	Spain	Prospective double-blind study, 12 weeks	60 children (6–14 yrs), 775 WSLs	CPP-ACP cream	CPP-ACPF; fluoride varnish; non-fluoridated paste	WSL appearance (digital image analysis)	CPP-ACPF most effective; CPP-ACP > fluoride varnish; limited effect on pits/fissures.
Güçlü et al., 2016	Turkey	RCT, 12 weeks	21 children (8–15 yrs), 101 WSLs	CPP-ACP paste twice daily	CPP-ACP + FV; fluoride varnish alone; control	Quantitative light-induced fluorescence (QLF)	CPP-ACP ± FV more effective than FV alone or control.
Mendes et al., 2018	Brazil	RCT, 3 months	36 children (5–13 yrs), 80 anterior teeth	CPP-ACP	Fluoride gel; CPP-ACP + fluoride	Visual index; lesion size	CPP-ACP + fluoride produced greatest remineralization.
Radha et al., 2020	India	RCT, 24 weeks	60 children with ECC	5% NaF + CPP-ACP varnish	5% NaF varnish	Lesion dimension; activity score	NaF + CPP-ACP achieved highest lesion inactivation.
Simon et al., 2022	India	RCT, 12 months	60 adolescents with post-orthodontic WSLs	CPP-ACP cream daily	Resin infiltration	Aesthetic improvement; lesion masking	Both effective; resin infiltration faster; CPP-ACP improved progressively.

DISCUSSION

Dental caries remains one of the most widespread oral health issues worldwide, particularly among children. The earliest sign of caries often appears as white spot lesions (WSLs), which indicate mineral loss beneath the enamel surface while the outer layer still appears intact. At this initial stage, these lesions can be reversed with good oral hygiene and the application of topical fluoride (37).

To manage and reverse such lesions, various remineralizing agents have been used - such as

fluoride, xylitol, bioactive glass, tricalcium phosphate, CPP, CPP-ACP and self-assembling peptides. (20, 38–40) Among these, Casein Phosphopeptide-Amorphous Calcium Phosphate (CPP-ACP) has gained significant attention. It works not only to remineralize enamel but also to reduce the risk of future cavities, making it an effective tool in both prevention and treatment. (41) CPP-ACP functions by stabilizing calcium and phosphate ions in a bioavailable amorphous form, preventing premature crystallization and maintaining a steady ion supply at the enamel surface. It mimics natural salivary proteins like statherin, which maintain calcium and phosphate

in solution and facilitate enamel repair. By creating a localized mineral reservoir, CPP-ACP helps restore enamel integrity by filling subsurface porosities characteristic of WSLs (42). Findings from the present systematic review consistently demonstrate that CPP-ACP is an effective therapeutic option for the management of WSLs in children. All six included clinical trials reported positive outcomes, although the extent of improvement varied depending on the patient population, study design, and application protocol. Despite the limited number of high-quality trials with low risk of bias, current evidence indicates that CPP-ACP achieves greater remineralization than placebo, conventional fluoridated toothpaste, or fluoride varnish alone. White spot lesions related to orthodontic treatment were also examined in the included literature. These lesions, which represent the earliest stage of the carious process, are particularly common in patients with fixed appliances due to the challenges of maintaining oral hygiene and changes in the local microecology.[25,26] Traditionally managed through invasive restorative approaches, WSLs are now increasingly being addressed through non-invasive methods. CPP-ACP, by maintaining calcium and phosphate ions in a supersaturated state at the enamel surface, offers a biological approach to reduce demineralization and promote remineralization.[27,28]

All six clinical trials included in this review demonstrated beneficial effects of CPP-ACP, although the magnitude varied across populations and protocols. Llana et al. reported that CPP-ACP combined with fluoride (CPP-ACFP) achieved the fastest and most significant improvements in smooth-surface lesions, with measurable changes as early as four weeks. CPP-ACP alone produced more gradual improvements, while fluoride varnish yielded intermediate results. Güçlü et al. confirmed that twice-daily CPP-ACP, with or without fluoride varnish, was more effective than varnish alone, emphasizing the importance of continuous daily application. In young children, Memarpour et al. demonstrated that parental application of CPP-ACP was effective in reducing lesion area and preventing progression of early childhood caries over 12 months. Similarly, Radha et al. showed that varnishes containing CPP-ACP achieved complete inactivation of lesions at six months, outperforming fluoride

varnish alone. In permanent dentition, Mendes et al. reported positive remineralization effects in non-orthodontic patients, while Simon et al. found that CPP-ACP improved post-orthodontic anterior WSLs progressively over time, although resin infiltration provided faster esthetic benefits. CPP-ACP demonstrated effectiveness across all stages of dentition. In primary dentition, Memarpour et al. and Radha et al. confirmed regression and inactivation of WSLs in toddlers and preschool children, highlighting its feasibility as a preventive tool for early childhood caries. In mixed dentition, Llana et al. and Güçlü et al. reported significant improvements in children aged 6–14 years, particularly on smooth surfaces. In permanent dentition, Simon et al. and Mendes et al. observed progressive remineralization and esthetic improvement, confirming its value even in high-risk adolescents and adults.

The site of WSLs influenced treatment response. Llana et al. found the most pronounced effects on smooth-surface lesions, with limited benefit in pits and fissures. Güçlü et al. reported lesion regression on buccal surfaces of both anterior and posterior teeth. Memarpour et al. and Radha et al. focused primarily on labial surfaces of primary anterior teeth, where CPP-ACP and CPP-ACP varnishes produced visible improvements. Simon et al. targeted anterior labial WSLs after orthodontic treatment, while Mendes et al. included both anterior and posterior permanent teeth, observing benefits across surfaces. These findings indicate that CPP-ACP is most effective on smooth, accessible enamel surfaces, whereas pits and fissures may require additional preventive strategies. The mode of CPP-ACP delivery varied and influenced clinical outcomes. Studies using twice-daily home application of CPP-ACP paste (Llana, Güçlü, Memarpour) demonstrated gradual but sustained lesion regression, underscoring the importance of compliance and frequency. Radha et al. used professional application of CPP-ACP varnish every three months, which produced rapid lesion inactivation within 24 weeks, suggesting that varnish formulations may achieve faster outcomes with less dependence on patient compliance. Simon et al. evaluated daily application of CPP-ACP cream for post-orthodontic lesions and reported progressive esthetic improvement over 12 months. Mendes et al. confirmed that regular topical application enhanced

remineralization of permanent teeth. Collectively, these findings indicate that professional varnish applications may provide faster results, while home-applied CPP-ACP requires consistent use over time for sustained benefits. Follow-up duration played a crucial role in observed effectiveness. Short-term trials (8–12 weeks) demonstrated early lesion regression, particularly with CPP-ACFP, which showed effects within four weeks. Longer studies of 6–12 months (Memarpour, Radha, Simon) reported more durable benefits, including complete lesion inactivation, sustained remineralization, and prevention of cavitation. These results highlight the cumulative benefit of prolonged CPP-ACP use and reinforce the need for long-term compliance to ensure clinical success.

CONCLUSION

CPP-ACP is a safe, effective, and non-invasive adjunct for managing white spot lesions in pediatric dentistry, particularly when combined with fluoride. It achieves the greatest benefits on smooth enamel surfaces with regular application. Clinicians should tailor treatment protocols balancing esthetic outcomes and lesion stability. Further well-designed, long-term RCTs with larger pediatric populations are needed to optimize use during active orthodontic treatment and preventive strategies.

Limitations and Clinical Implications

Despite encouraging results, several limitations should be noted. Sample sizes were small in some studies, follow-up times were inconsistent, and outcome assessment methods varied widely. Home-use compliance was not uniformly monitored, which may have influenced outcomes. Importantly, only one trial specifically addressed post-orthodontic WSLs, and preventive use during active orthodontic treatment remains underexplored. From a clinical standpoint, CPP-ACP is a safe, effective, and non-invasive adjunct for managing WSLs across primary, mixed, and permanent dentitions. Its benefits appear strongest on smooth-surface lesions and when used either daily at home or as part of professional varnish protocols. Combination with fluoride often enhances outcomes, though results were not universally superior. Future well-designed randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes, standardized

diagnostic criteria, and longer follow-up are essential to optimize application protocols and confirm preventive benefits.

Strength of this systematic review

This study focuses exclusively on pediatric patients and including only randomized controlled trials, it provides clinically relevant and high-quality evidence. Furthermore, the comprehensive database search, structured risk of bias assessment, and consistent findings across studies strengthen the reliability of the conclusions while highlighting important gaps for future research.

Conflict of Interest:

None.

Acknowledgment:

I sincerely thank my guide for invaluable guidance and unwavering support throughout this work. I also express my heartfelt gratitude to my colleagues for their constant encouragement, insightful suggestions, and collaborative spirit, which significantly contributed to the successful completion of this study. Their help was truly appreciated.

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HOW TO CITE: Sandhya Karak, Prachi Pathak, Mousumi Goswami, Aditya Saxena, Mriganka Kumar Phukan, Ananya Sharma, Prachi Singhal, Ajay Khanna, CPP-ACP And Its Effectiveness On White Spot Lesions In Pediatric Patients: A Systematic Review, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (1), 954-962. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18283529>

